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The Effectiveness of Village Councils in Land Conflicts Management in Tanzania: A Reflection of Kondoa District Council.

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Abstract

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This Paper assessed the effectiveness of village councils on land conflict management in Tanzania. A cross-sectional design and mixed research approach were employed for the study. Yamane's 1967 Formula helped get respondents, where 127 respondents were randomly selected and gathered information. The reason for using Yamane is that the population was known and fixed in a selected study area (Yamen, 1967). The main inference is; village councils are somehow efficient in land conflict management. Such status is associated with the challenges the respective organ encounters, including corrupt behaviour of village leaders, low knowledge of land laws, poor land use plans, and poor community involvement in land resource allocation. The Paper has practical, theoretical and policy necessities as it makes a new guide, provides policy inputs and enhanced foundations in land conflict management. To mitigate land conflicts, the Paper recommends that district authority, particularly the management, institute capacity-building strategies to implant knowledge on Land regulations and the law of inheritance to the village council and the community. Land management activities should be fully funded by the central government rather than financed by the lower level of local government, whose financial capacity is scrawny. Lastly, communities need extensive engagement to own the process and conceptualize the constraints associated with the land. In contrast, land laws should be enforced to help people have discipline and respect for the land.

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1.0. Introduction

Conflict over scarce land resources is a perplexing touch matter that escalates tensions globally; for instance, the conflict between Israelis and Palestinians is over who gets what land and how it is controlled. Accordingly, this has necessitated unique initiatives and strategies for preventing and mitigating the respective conflicts, particularly in the global arena, whereby different mediations and resolutions are passed, for instance, the 1968 U.N. Security Council Resolution number 262 that condemned Israel for its premeditated military action in violation of its obligation under the Charter and the cease-fire resolutions. It issued a solemn warning to Israel that, if there were a repeat incident, the Council would have to consider further steps to enforce its decisions and considered that Lebanon has suffered over land skirmishes and responsibility rests with Israel (The United Nations Charter, 1945). Despite such Council Resolutions being a measure for mitigating the conflict, the conflict still permeates with each side attacking the other for territorial control; allegedly, the Council is conceived as toothless and incapable of mitigating the Israel-Palestinian conflict, thus the conflict still persists.

Conflicts over the scramble to land have caused wars in Liberia and Sierra Leone, and the approximately 25-year Conflicts in Sri Lanka fought over geographic claims to an ethnic motherland for the country's marginal people (Collier et al, 2006). In this case, a conflict resolution strategy to address actual land conflicts is a historical, customary traditional practice. Therefore, governments at varying levels have instituted laws and land tribunals as management avenues anchored on by local and international communities. The respective conflict prevention and resolution strategies are geared to institute and enforce tranquillity, stability and anticipation of serenity and harmony in areas potential to land resource rivalry. The initiatives are labelled as "preventive" actions looking to mitigate the potential of conflict and set the ground for dealing with indicators and actual conflicts, namely conflict Management (FAO, 2019).

In Africa, Wehrmann (2008), in his piece namely Mitigating Land Resources Conflict in Africa, contends the fact that government authorities in most counties in the continent deviate substantial resources in uplifting land governance, having with other aims to mitigate overreaching and escalating land conflicts via effective land laws. The respective writer believes land disputes can be prevented and mitigated through a comprehensive all-inclusive strategic mechanism and methodology. Wehrmann (2008), in his revision, applauded that numerous and supplementary land conflicts are the results of manifold sales and dual apportionment of land, either because of legal heterogeneity or informal, traditional occupancy or associated with striving by state-legalized agencies with a similar mandate on land allocation. Ojalammi (2006) maintained that conflicts at a village level had been perpetrated because of favouritism and double standards in the sense that more land is allocated to crop farmers while livestock keepers are ignored; therefore, a need for harmonized land allocation to prevent escalation and resolve prevalent land conflicts in Africa as elsewhere in the world.

Ujoh (2014) studied land conflicts in Nigeria; he pointed out that land fights are connected with increasing population growth, resulting in environmental ruin and unprecedented trends of local, regional and global change in the climate. He proposed that I wisely utilize land assets in a viable way, shielding the settings, biodiversity, and world macroclimate are essential measures to prevent further conflict escalation. Ogola (2013) reasoned that villages are confronted with irregular land allocation, which has triggered discomfort at the village level. The responsible authorities alleged misconduct, including dishonesty and stereotypes over land issues. He (Ibid: 2013) added that the giving power and authority to local authorities in the decentralization policy has further disjointed the ward, and districts and created pseudo gods to poorly misuse unquestionably the land resources at lower level, this culminate into further escalation of land

conflicts by users. This situation in Nigeria differs from the Tanzania village land Act number 5, 1999, which stipulates that a village authority council shall not allocate land or grant a customary tenancy right without a preceding commendation of the village meeting. Pkalya, Mohamed, and Isabella (2003) in the study disclose that, notwithstanding the fact that the sources of land fights are interconnected and symbiotic, there is a necessity of forming connections amongst tactical interventions, the core causes of fights and highpoint the roles and tasks of participants in the peace process.

In the context of East Africa, Nindi et al. (2014), in the research about land snatching conducted in the Republic of Uganda was of the view that battles of land have risen amongst associates of the local citizens; this is enhanced by the allocation of land aimed at palm oil cultivation. Citizens are driven away from their households to woodland to pave the way for alternative palm farming, which escalates tensions. Todorovski, D., Zevenbergen and Van der Molen (2012) said there is inadequate cognizance of both the costs of pathetic governance in public land administration; community land is often handled as free, but in terms of location, utility and service distribution is infrequent and appreciated. Therefore, there is a lack of transparency and accountability in a land transaction, particularly when it comes to the transfer process of state-owned land into private ownership; this signal some corrupt practice malpractice which is illegal. Similarly, in other nations, the issue of land rights in Tanzania is a historical, long memorial characterizing the period before and after colonialism. Yamano and Deininger (2005) contend that land fights in Tanzania throughout the preceding decades were mitigated by utilizing the then-casual institutions such as clan leaders, groups, local monarchs, and chiefs. The respective scholar then recommended a highbred or blended approach of formal approaches (traditional monarchs, heads, assemblages) and informal approaches (village land commission, village council, police militaries and judges) regimes to be used chronologically in land fight management.

The United Republic of Tanzania Local Government Act No. 7 of 1982 stretches authority to the village council in all village community matters. Since the village councils have the paramount prerogative on the entire village land, they can allocate part of the land to the village. The Tanzania Village Land Act, number 5 of 1999, denotes the governance and administration of village land, constituting 70 per cent of the whole land mass of Tanzania (URT, 1999). The respective Act provides power to the village councils to establish Village Land councils entrusted with resolving land conflicts in the respective vicinity. The organs closer to the grassroots community are expected to mitigate land conflicts at the initial (Conflict Prevention) stages to avoid escalation into deadlock stages. Unsettled disputes at the respective organs (Village council) would be channelled to the ward committee and the District Land and Housing Tribunals where needed. Despite such arrangements, land conflicts persistently escalate in Kondo and other parts of the United Republic of Tanzania (John, 2017). The persistence of Conflicts between crop farmers and pastoralists in different parts of the United Republic of Tanzania evidences the scenario. An example of such unending conflicts which some districts encounter entail; Bunda, Mvomero, Kilombero, Kilindi, Loliondo, Simanjiro, and Mbarali districts in the United Republic of Tanzania (Mwamfupe, 2015). This Paper aimed at bridging this practical gap by assessing the effectiveness of village councils in land conflict management in Tanzania, using the Kondo district council as the case study and recommend practical, policy and theoretical inputs to enhance functionality of the village organs in mitigating land conflicts.

1.1. Theoretical and Empirical Explanations

The Paper is underpinned by Social conflict theory, a Marxist-based theory with the view that a society is in a state of long-lasting conflict due to competition for limited resources. It sees society as fragmented into groups that compete for social and economic resources; individuals

and groups within a society have differing amounts of material and non-material resources (the wealthy vs the poor). This competition creates social disorder and hence conflicts. Marx believes that social order is maintained by domination and power rather than by agreement and conformity. He further gives that social orders are maintained by domination with power in the hands of those with significant political, economic and social resources.

Those with wealth and power try to hold on by suppressing the poor and the powerless. He says there is no agreement in the conflict settlements because of the power imbalance between the two parties. The conflict theory by Marx teaches that one of the primary sources of conflicts in society is the scarcity of resources, of which land is one of those potential resources. This implies that land conflict in any social setting is inevitable due to the scarcity of land, making it necessary to have a substantial land conflict resolution body, in this study, a village council. Another vital point to note from this theory is the power imbalance in the course of struggling for these scarce resources, which may result in conflict; it might adversely affect the community members in the sense that those who are powerless in the struggle are likely to lose at the expense of those who are politically, economically and influentially powerful (Kishenyi, 2017).

This might be true in land conflict resolution institutions where the most influential people in the community may influence the decisions of land conflict resolution bodies. This reduces the trust of the community in these bodies. However, under customary conflict resolution mechanisms where the conflicts are resolved under traditional norms, values and beliefs, the issue of influence from the influential people in the community may not be possible, which is contrary to Marx's beliefs. Also, Marx disagrees with the consensual approaches in dispute resolution, which again is contrary to the mechanism used by the customary laws to resolve conflict through mediation, one of the consensual approaches mechanisms (Kalande, 2008).

Conversely, Mtwale (2002) elucidates the recklessness of the government powers on land conflict management. From his perspective, the lack of proactive capacity on the side of the government of Tanzania's incredibly immediate response by an early signal when a dispute occurs is very detrimental. The writer points out corruption and the government's stillness as the main cradles of land struggles. Rubakula, Wang, and Wei (2019) contend that the villages council's deficiency of an efficient established procedure which could support formulate the foundation for all players to become intricate in the decision procedures as a consequence, struggles occur in the existence of indigenous organizations including village councils, ward committees and district councils empowered by legislation and enforced by strategies to assume mitigation and management in their ranges of dominion. The result is a perpetuation of conflict at local level rather than mitigating the respective conflicts.

Crook (2004) believes that the unproportioned population increase in the availability of land is the main trigger of land resource conflicts around the world. Such conflicts have invited different mitigation strategies in rural areas of the United Republic of Tanzania. The writers have recognized traditional practice methodology, one of the dispute perseverance instruments in Tanzania, to show a leading protagonist in conveying tranquillity and harmony amongst adherents of the social order. In their research, Emanuel and Ndimbwa (2013) recommended reducing land disputes by applying and adopting new technology in farming and livestock keeping. Also, knowledge and skills should be availed to society members on the advanced mechanism of animal keeping and crop farming to ankle on quality and not quantity use of land for supreme productivity.

Gwaleba (2019) established that people multiplication fostered development engagement and undertakings amongst citizens, and agriculturalists, livestock keepers, and entrepreneurs are

drivers of land resource conflicts. The respective study provides that such conflicts could be mitigated through a holistic approach which considers the dreams and expectations of our future population segments in approaching problems of our present and future times. In their study, Darling and Earl Walker (2001) concluded that interviewees do not comprehensively understand any provision central to land resources. The respondent additionally demonstrated indifference to such law as conceived to have no effects to protect them from land malpractice at the grassroots level. Unfortunately, the respondent asserts that land is being grabbed from them unnecessarily on the condition that it is designated under the planned small-town services. Therefore, the Paper is necessitated by a drive to assess village council effectiveness in mitigating land disputes in Tanzania, figure out any challenges and recommend policy, legal and practical measures to achieve peace at the grassroots community level.

Conceivably, the empirical and theoretical review shows that village councils' effectiveness in land conflict management is not well assessed. That being the case, the Paper aimed at bridging this practical gap by assessing the effectiveness of village councils in land conflict management in Tanzania, using the Kondoa district council as the case study. This provides an avenue to recommend a mechanism for enhancing the village council institution to foster harmony and tranquillity in land utility within the Unit Republic of Tanzania.

2.0. Methodology

The Paper got information from the Kondoa district council within the United Republic of Tanzania. The Kondoa district was selected because the area has had frequent land conflicts between farmers and cattle for a substantial time. The Paper used a cross-sectional research design. According to Kothari (2004), the respective design has the benefit of collecting data to make inferences about the population of interest at one point in time, yielding maximal information.

A mixed approach was employed, which combined, complemented and triangulated data for accuracy and alternative explanation to confirm the validity of the research findings (Kombo & Tromp, 2006). The Paper used Yamane 1967 Formula to get respondents, where a total of 127 respondents were randomly selected and involved in gathering information, whereby 96 were for questionnaires while 31 were for in-depth interviews and discussions. The Total Population of Kondoa was 1541 (2012, Census). Respectively, Quantitative data were analysed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. MS Excel 2007 was used to analyse the data, derived from descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages), while inferential statistics were presented in tables. On the other hand, qualitative data were subjected to content analysis, and the findings were presented in narrative form to support quantitative data. The combination of the narrative and tables' presentation improved the clarity of the finding and the validity of inferences.

3.0. Results and Discussions

The Paper's main objective was to assess the effectiveness of village councils on land conflict management in Tanzania and elucidate the challenges confronting village councils in land conflict management. This was important because it would provide an avenue to improve such councils and become sound and reliable in managing conflicts at the lower level. Taking Kondoa District Commissioner's Official report revealed that the year between 2019 to March 2021, the office received 130 complaints related to land conflicts; in 2020, 45 complaints were received from the five villages and in 2021, the number increased to 50 complaints, while from January up to March 2022, 32 complaints were received at Kondoa District .

3.1. Effectiveness of the Village Councils in Land Conflict Management

The Paper wanted to know how practical the village councils were in land dispute resolutions. The results were; 70.8% of the respondents argued that the village councils were somehow effective in solving land disputes, so some of the conflicts occurring are sent to the District Commissioner for resolution. These results concur with the explanations given by the interviewee, Kondo District Land Officer, on April 11th 2022, in his office noted that,

"Village councils are not so effective in handling land conflicts because they lack knowledge of land laws and are suspected of corruption practices in their resolutions. As a result, people prefer to use ward tribunals or report to the District Commissioner for resolution. Also, most of the solutions given by the village councils are not documented, hence when the new councils come in after the election, there is a tendency to nullify most of the decisions made by the former village councils, especially when the new village councils are from another political party different from the former one."

Besides, the findings in Table 01 below indicate that 20% of the respondents said that the village governments are very effective, and 8.3% said they are ineffective in their performance. This finding was supported by the interview held on April 12th 2022, at Kwamtoro division with the division officer who said that,

"Most of the time, the district Commissioner assigns me to handle land conflicts in my division, and sometimes the district commissioner herself deals with those conflicts while the village councils are there."

Table 1.0 Effectiveness of the V.C.s

	Frequency	Per cent
Not effective	8	8.3
Somehow effective	68	70.8
Very effective	20	20.8
Total	96	100

Source: Field Data 2022:

3.2. Challenges Facing Village Councils

Any action taken in the organization there is most probable a resultant challenge. The challenges need to be identified to address them smoothly or may hinder and deter the performance of the respective organization. As the legal institutions for land dispute resolution at village levels, the village councils may have encountered some challenges that affect their performance.

The Paper employed open-ended questions to capture several challenges, which during information capturing were classified into seven categories; these include; low level of knowledge on land laws, poor enforcement of Land laws, poor land use plan in the villages, poor community involvement in village resource allocation, corrupt behaviours of the council members, lack of resources to run the village offices and poor support from the central government. The results are presented in Table 2.0 below.

The results from Table 2.0 below indicate that 21.9% of the respondents said that a low level of knowledge of land laws is one of the challenges which affected the performance of the village

councils, especially on land conflict resolution. These findings are in line with explanations given by the Agricultural Officer in his office on May 14th, 2022, who said that,

"Village leaders lack education and knowledge on land laws and are also corrupted as their decisions are mostly biased. The agricultural officer went further by arguing that land does not increase. However, people and cattle increase daily, so the government should put extra effort into training the community in mechanized agriculture and livestock keeping, whereby people would use small land and produce much. Also, because of the land conflicts emanating daily, the government should establish a land office at the village level like other sectors such as education and health; this could help solve land conflicts at the initial stage."

About 6.3% of the respondents said there is poor land law enforcement by the village leaders. The findings concur with the explanations given by the legal officer in her office on May 15th 2022. During the interview, she said,

"Village councils, through their village land councils, have no legal mandate to give judgment on matters related to land conflict, but they are required to mediate the conflicting parties amicably. Because of that, some people do not trust the village government. Also, she added that most of the resolutions handled by the village councils are not written; they are just oral agreements which later on, especially when the village leaders change, the conflicts may rise again and sometimes are resolved differently."

The findings are supported by the study done by Ogola (2013), who observed that weak and ineffective institutions to affect natural resource management policies/laws and regulations at the lower levels have created more resource conflicts.

About 20.8% of the respondents said there is a poor land use plan in the study area. As a result, land conflicts are prevailing. The findings are in line with the words of the District land Valuer in an interview on May 20th 2022, who said that,

"Village land is not surveyed and hence causes conflict between farmers and livestock keepers and between one individual and another. This happens because everyone thinks he/she has the right to use the land the way he/she wants. The livestock keepers prefer the land for grazing while the peasants prefer the land for agriculture."

About 19.8% of the respondents said that poor community involvement in village resource allocation leads to land conflicts in the study area. The findings concur with the general observation during A Focus Group Discussion at Kwamtoro Ward on May 10th 2022, which came out that,

"Most of the time, village leaders do not involve the community during land allocation or conflict resolution. They behave so because of personal interests and do not present the decisions made to the village assembly as required by law."

About 20.8% of the respondents said that the village leaders are corrupt, so land conflicts are not solved legally but have some biases. The findings concur with the general observation during A Focus Group Discussion at Kwamtoro Ward on May 16th, 2022, which came out that,

"Governance is abysmal at the village level. Village leaders assume power and misuse it. The land has become a source of adverse income for them. People without money are suffering. Some people use the land to get leadership because during campaigns,

they try to win the voters by promising to provide land to those with no land, and when they win, they start grabbing land whenever they can, including citizen's land."

About 10.4% of the respondents argued that lack of resources and support to run the offices led to poor performance of the village councils and sometimes engaged in corruption to compensate for the deficit. The Human Resource Officer on May 17th, 2022, supported the findings by saying that,

"Resource constraints regarding village executive officers trigger conflicts; such officials need fuel and stationeries to run and manage the office, which they sometimes do not get. These are among the challenges that hinder the effectiveness of land disputes at village levels. He added that lack of fuel at the district level makes the human resource officer, land and legal officers fail to visit village councils, see their operations, and give advice on good governance."

Table 2.0 below illustrates this clearly. From the findings, the challenges which are facing village councils.

Table 2.0. Challenges Facing V.C.s in Reducing Land Conflict

	Frequency	Per cent
Corrupt behaviours of the village leaders	20	20.8
Poor enforcement of land laws	6	6.3
Low level of knowledge of land laws	21	21.9
Poor land use plan	20	20.8
Poor community involvement in village resource allocation	19	19.8
Lack of resources to run the village governments	10	10.4
Total	96	100.0

Source: Field Data 2022

4.0. Conclusions And Recommendations

4.1. Conclusions

The Paper assessed the effectiveness of the village councils on land conflict management in Tanzania. The area of the study was the Kondo District Councils. In carrying out the study, the status of land conflicts in the Kondo District was reportedly documented in the District Commissions report; this established the base of the Argument. The findings show that there are still land conflicts in the Kondo District Council despite resolution strategies being in place, particularly village council bodies.

Moreover, the Paper has established that the village councils are moderately capable of managing land conflicts in Kondo District Council. Although natural conflicts are unhealthy since they are opposed to development, importantly, land conflicts are dangerous as human life depends entirely on land. This calls for a more transformational approach in mitigating them, while the village council should be more efficient in managing land conflicts to ensure development.

However, the Paper has inferred that challenges of the village councils are mainly the low level of knowledge on land laws, corrupt behaviour of the village leaders, poor land use plan, poor community involvement in village resource allocation, lack of resources to run the village government and ineffectiveness of land law enforcement. Therefore, such challenges must be

sensitized over stakeholders' government as key and addressed for the village councils' effectiveness. Thus, This can ensure peace and tranquillity amongst land stakeholders at the village level, mainly amongst farmers and livestock keepers who are highly affected in Kondoa districts and Tanzania.

4.2 Recommendations

Therefore, the paper cements that people need these organs to continue operating but recommends that they should be improved. They should be facilitated financially and in terms of capacity building on knowledge and skill. They should be trained on land laws as well as on mediation procedures. Furthermore, the land sector should be regarded as a special sector, as the government does to other sectors like education, water, roads and health sectors. Thus, allocate enough funds from the central government rather than depending on the district's source to run this sector. The community, in particular the village, should participate fully and must understand the challenges facing citizens related to land resources and participate in resolving conflicts in their locality.

The government should ensure that all villages have village executive officers (VEOs). Because these educated ones would help to interpret land laws and guide effectively the village governments rather than the current situation where many villages have acting VEOs who have been put in by the village chairperson and whose performance is not effective. The paper further recommends, the Ministry of Land and TAMISEMI must come together with other ministries like the Ministry of Natural Resources and the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock and harmonize their policies and laws to avoid possible contradictions. Such gaps in policy positions particularly on land utility are catalyst for continued conflicts in Kondoa districts as well as other districts in the United Republic of Tanzania.

The village chairpersons must be paid some allowances as the councillors are paid, rather than working as a volunteer for five years. This situation invites them to engage in corrupt behaviours. This brings into attention the United Nations' conceived ineffectiveness in mitigating global conflict, as also is associated with lack of its own financial resources and appropriate human resources, as who pays the piper chooses the tune, thus The UN is controlled by big powers because they are the one financing its operations. The village councils are controlled by those who bribe financially.

In order to make sure that people understand land laws, the Paper recommends that the ministry responsible for land should spread awareness about land laws and policy through different media like public televisions and leaflets. Moreover, effective land use plans should be implemented in the area of the study and other areas in the country. This will demarcate clear boundaries and provide clear land needs. By doing so, it will help to minimize land conflicts to a large extent.

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POLICY BRIEF

The article assessed the effectiveness of village councils in land conflict management in Tanzania a reflection of Kondo district. This piece was important as the respective organs are strategically placed and function to mitigate conflict and consequently act as catalyst for social, political and economic prosperity at the local arena. Likewise, by Taking into account the sensitivity of the perplexing issue within village council, reflected via the challenges encountered in such organ to mention a few: financial cconstraints and lack of knowledge and skill by some village council members. Lack of special treatment of land sector then regard of it to be like any other sector such as education, water, roads and health. And indeed inadequate community (Village) participation which weakens their understanding on issues related to land resources and thus unable to resolve conflicts in their locality. This research article therefore has both practical, policy and professional briefs as follows:

Practically the article admits the fact that, these organs are inevitable at village council level, that they should be facilitated financially and in terms of capacity building on knowledge and skill. Specifically, the council members should be trained on land laws as well as on mediation and arbitration procedures to act proactively in mitigating land conflict at community level.

Furthermore, the land sector should be regarded as a special sector, therefore it has to be given weight in the same dimension like other sectors of education, water, roads and health. In this case, allocate with enough funds from the central government rather than depending on the district's source to run this sector of which practically don't suffice the requirement to execute planned activities and programs of the respective councils.

The community, in particular the village, should participate fully and must understand the development challenges facing citizens related to land resources and participate in resolving conflicts in their locality. Rather than, relying on central government official like District and Regional Commissioners who at most time are occupied with tense administrative and political pressure.

The village chairpersons must be paid some allowances as the councilors are paid, rather than working as a volunteer for five years of their political services. This situation invites them to engage in corrupt behaviors. Besides, the government should ensure that all villages have village executive officers (VEOs). Because these educated ones would help to interpret land laws and guide effectively the village governments rather than the current situation where many villages have acting VEOs who have been put in by the village chairperson and whose performance is not effective.

Policy wise the Ministry of Land and TAMISEMI must come together with other ministries like the Ministry of Natural Resources and the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock and harmonize their policies and laws to avoid possible contradictions and double standard. Such gaps in policy positions particularly on land utility are catalyst for continued conflicts in Kondo districts as well as other districts in the United Republic of Tanzania.

Additionally, the ministry responsible for land should spread awareness about land laws and policy through different media like public televisions and leaflets. Moreover, Effective land use plans should be implemented in the area of the study and other areas in the country. This will demarcate clear boundaries and provide land needs. By doing so, it will help to minimize land conflicts to a large extent.

Lastly, the government should diversify a payment policy so that, the village chairpersons should be paid some allowances as the councilors are paid, rather than working as a volunteer for five years. This situation invites them to engage in corrupt behaviors. This brings into attention the United Nations' conceived ineffectiveness in mitigating global conflict, as also is associated with lack of its own financial resources, as who pays the piper chooses the tune. Thus the UN is controlled by big powers because they are the one financing its operations. The village councils are controlled by those who bribe financially.